

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF EMBEDDED INTERROGATOR GEOMETRY ON STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a finite element method is presented capable of predicting the influence an embedded interrogator has on the structural performance of the composite host. It starts with the development of a methodology capable of predicting the resin pocket geometry surrounding the inclusion, and the subsequent creation of a cured part used for loading simulations. The obtained results are compared to experimental force-displacement curves obtained on several composite samples with embedded interrogators of different geometries under a 3-point bending load, developed within the EU FP7 SmartFiber project. A very good correspondence between experimental and numerical data is obtained, both in the prediction of the resin pocket geometry as well as the resulting force-displacement curves. A consequence of the developed modelling technique is that it allows the numerical study of shape optimization of embedded structures in order to minimize the detrimental effects of the inclusion on the structural performance of the composite structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past couple of decades, composite materials have received a significant amount of attention from both the research community as well as industry. Their high strength-to-weight ratio make them ideally suited materials for high-performance and demanding applications. However, their fibrous and layered nature inevitably results in a strong orthotropic material response and complex failure mechanisms. As these complex failure mechanisms are (at present) hard to predict accurately, non-destructive testing techniques have become an important area of interest and research for composite materials.

Amongst the many different non-destructive testing techniques, optical fiber sensors hold a special place. Their small dimensions (commercial fibers are available with diameters of 80-125 μ m while research is continuously decreasing this diameter), immunity to EM-fields, high temperature resistance,... coupled with their fibrous nature make them ideally suited for embedding purposes in (fibrous) composite materials. In addition to only being minimally disruptive to the host material, embedding the optical fiber sensors during manufacture gives them the unique capability of providing information on the stress/strain state of the composite host over its entire life-span, including manufacture during which (important) residual strains can be created. A deployed sensor network based on these optical fiber sensors can therefore provide continuous health-monitoring information, in order to guarantee the safe operation of the composite structure over its entire life-span and timely maintenance when necessary.

While the optical fiber sensors are robust enough to withstand the harsh conditions involved with composite manufacturing (temperature, vacuum, pressure), current commercial read-out equipment (called '*interrogators*') are not. As a result, the optical fiber sensors need to exit the composite host in order to connect to an interrogator for read-out purposes. The fragile egress point that is formed where the thin optical fiber line leaves the composite, is vulnerable to damage (and loss of the sensor connection) during manipulations of the structure. In addition, this sensor line connection to a fixed read-out system makes the sensor technique hard to use in rotary applications such as turbine blades. (Note that optical equivalents to electrical slip-rings are not common in optical fiber applications) At

present, this limitation has held back the industrial uptake of optical fiber sensing and mostly limited the use of this sensing technique to research laboratories. The European Union FP7 ‘SmartFiber’ project (2010 – 2014) set out to resolve this issue by successfully developing a fully embeddable and miniaturized optical fiber interrogator using state-of-the-art photonic techniques. Power and data-transmission occur using wireless technology. This solution effectively creates a ‘smart’ composite structures with no external leads and perfectly suited for rotary applications.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

While the concept of creating an embeddable interrogator system is straight-forward, the influences on mechanical response of the host material with embedded system must be assessed carefully. While the polymer matrix becomes fluid during manufacture, the fibrous reinforcements remain solid and as a result cannot drape perfectly around an (arbitrary) inclusion. This is illustrated in Figure 1, showing the occurrence of a resin-rich zone (called ‘*resin pocket*’) surrounding an optical fiber sensor embedded in a cross-ply carbon fiber laminate.

Figure 1: Resin pocket surrounding embedded optical fiber sensor

Several researchers have investigated the influence of these resin pockets on structural response of the surrounding host material [1-6]. Shivakumar et al. [4] found that these resin-rich zones can induce strength reductions of up to -40% in static compression tests. Surgeon et al. [5] found that a strong influence could be observed in bending experiments. Lee et al. [6] found that fatigue behaviour was affected by the presence of an optical fiber sensor. The common denominator of all these research papers is that the resin pocket can have a significant effect on the structural performance of the host. Clearly, before a large structure such as an interrogator can be embedded safely in a composite host, the impact on the structural performance must be analysed.

In this work, a finite element approach will be presented to (i) predict the resin pocket geometry during manufacture of a composite with an arbitrary inclusion, and (ii) to simulate the mechanical response of the composite with embedded structure under mechanical loads. The results will be compared to microscopic cross-sections of embedded structures and to load-displacement curves of experimental samples with embedded interrogators.

3 INTERROGATOR AND COMPOSITE SPECIFICATIONS

3.1 Interrogator geometries and materials

As the resin pocket geometry has a significant influence on the resulting material response, it stands to reason that not all inclusion geometries have an equal effect on the structural strength of the composite. Consequently, - given a certain set of boundary conditions and additional requirements – an optimal resin pocket geometry should exist, minimizing the influence on the structural strength. At the onset of the SmartFiber project, a F.E. model was built with material parameters tuned to obtain approximate resin pocket geometries as found in several experimental samples with embedded optical

fiber sensors. Although this F.E. simulation had no physically meaningful material properties, it was found to give a rough first approximation of the resin pocket geometry for a few simple cases.

This simplified model was used as a first attempt to optimize the interrogator geometry. Several parametric geometries were simulated with an objective function to minimize the total resin pocket area. Figure 2 shows the optimal resin pocket geometry obtained according to these simulations, leading to a minimal resin pocket geometry.

Figure 2: Optimal interrogator geometry

In order to assess whether this “optimal” geometry was indeed significantly better than any random geometry, it will be compared to a pure square inclusion with equal thickness. In addition, the influence of interrogator material will be investigated by using a stiff (epoxy) and flexible (silicone) material for the inclusion. The corresponding material properties are given in Table 1.

	Epoxy	Silicone
E-modulus (MPa)	2730	4.05
Poisson ratio (-)	0.37	0.50

Table 1: Interrogator material properties

3.2 Composite material properties and lay-up

In this work, a Hexcel HexPly M34N/G-136x5 glass-fiber epoxy prepreg was used. The stacking was chosen to be $[0_2, +45, 90, -45]_s$, with the interrogator embedded between the outer 0-degree plies. This lay-up was chosen to be representative for a tidal turbine blade lay-up (envisaged as a feasible application for the SmartFiber system), while being sufficiently thin to allow testing up to fracture using the available machines at the department. The (cured) properties of the prepreg material are given in Table 2.

E_{11}	36 GPa
E_{22}	13 GPa
G_{12}	4 GPa
ν_{12}	0.313

Table 2: In-plane material properties of M34N/G-136x5

In order to perform finite element simulations, the through-thickness (3-direction) properties of the prepreg are required. As these were not measured experimentally and their influence on the specific load cases are expected to be minimal, some assumptions were made: $E_{33} = E_{22}$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.3$.

The pure M34N epoxy (filling the resin pocket during forming) was modeled as having a stiffness of $E=3.8$ GPa according to the datasheet information.

4 TEST COUPON MANUFACTURING

The experimental samples are made out of HexPly M34N/G-136x5 in a $[0_2, +45, 90, -45]_s$ lay-up. Large plates of dimensions 400 x 300 mm were manufactured. The different interrogators (extrusions

of the profile shown in Figure 2 and a rectangular cross-section with the same height) were embedded in between the top 0 degree layers.

The samples were cured using the vacuum bagging technique in an out-of-autoclave procedure as recommended by the manufacturer. After curing, the plates were cut via a water-jet process to obtain tests specimens with dimensions of 400 x 30 mm with the inclusion located at 1/3rd the length of the sample. Additionally, small strips of these plates were cut and polished in order to observe the resin pockets surrounding the inclusion.

5 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

The material properties during curing are significantly different from those of a cured composite material. As the resin pocket is created at the early stages of matrix polymerization, the resin pocket predictions and cured material response cannot be captured by a single F.E. model and material model. Consequently two separate simulations are performed in sequence: (i) in a first simulation the cured composite geometry (including a resin pocket) is simulated with uncured material properties, simulating the draping of the composite layers around the inclusion, and subsequently (ii) the cured composite geometry with cured material properties is used to simulate the mechanical loading conditions.

5.1 Resin pocket prediction

Modelling the resin pocket geometry surrounding the SmartFiber interrogator requires the simulation of the forming behaviour of the composite during the curing cycle. While research is available on large scale draping simulation approaches using custom-coded user elements [7-9], these approaches require an extensive amount of material characterization, coding efforts and advanced understanding of computational mechanics to derive a physically meaningful simulation result. The intention of the work presented here, is to develop a straight-forward finite element approach available to a wide range of researchers, including those focussing on experimental mechanics with a limited knowledge of finite element techniques. The challenge then, is to derive a modelling approach capable of capturing the material response during curing, using only standard finite element formulations and material models available within the ABAQUS software package.

Standard element formulations within ABAQUS all assume that bending stiffness can be derived from the in-plane properties. This assumption severely over-estimates the bending stiffness of a composite material during the curing stage, at which point the resin is in a low-viscosity state. At this point, the individual reinforcements do not act as a single material, but are free to slide over each other during bending. As a result, the bending stiffness of a prepreg laminate during curing is significantly lower than what would be modelled using standard element formulations in ABAQUS (i.e. derived from the high in-plane stiffness resulting from the glass-fiber reinforcement). In order to overcome this issue, a single ply is modelled in ABAQUS as a series of sub-plyes which are free to slide over each other. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Finite element modelling approach of bending response of an uncured prepreg

As a result of this approach, the individual sub-plyes have in-plane properties corresponding to the (uncured) material properties, while the bending stiffness of the entire ply can be tuned by changing the number of sub-plyes contained within one ply. The bending behaviour is extracted from a series of

cantilever beam tests: an uncured material sample is fixed at one end and allowed to bend under gravity load while it is curing. The vertical displacement of the sample after curing is recorded in order to extract the bending response of the ply. Note that as large deformations are involved, beam theory can no longer be used and a more advanced formulation as presented in [10] should be used.

The necessary material properties of the uncured laminate are derived based on information obtained from datasheets and literature. The uncured material properties used in the simulation of the resin pockets are given in Table 3.

Number of sub-plyies	11
E_{11}	34 GPa
E_{22}	4 GPa
E_{33}	50 MPa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$	0.5
G_{12}	2 GPa
$G_{13} = G_{23}$	30 MPa

Table 3: Uncured material properties of M34N/G-136x5

The uncured laminate is modeled as a series of flat, horizontal plyies with an inclusion in between. The model exploits all symmetry available to reduce the computational times and uses a generalized plane strain approach as the inclusion profile is an extrusion of the shape shown in Figure 2. External loads representing gravity and internal vacuum inside the vacuum bag are added to represent the loading conditions during forming.

5.2 Bending load response

At the completion of the resin pocket geometry calculations, a cured geometry is obtained. In order to be able to simulate loading conditions on the cured laminate, a couple of additional steps is required. First of all, the material model used, should be switched from the uncured properties (Table 3) to the cured properties (Table 2). Additionally, the F.E. simulation of the draping and resin pocket creation assumes a solid material behaviour. As a result, while the resin pocket is predicted, the simulation does not include the filling of this resin pocket area with resin from the surrounding laminate. Consequently, new material must be added inside the resin pocket, representing the cured matrix material. In order to achieve these steps, the cured geometry was exported and imported into a new model in which the correct material properties were defined and the resin pocket was filled with material. This model could then be used subsequently to model loading conditions on the laminate.

As a tidal turbine blade application was envisaged within the SmartFiber project, a loading condition representative to actual loading conditions was chosen. The choice was made to perform a series of three-point bending tests. By using a three-point bending load, the location of maximum moment could be chosen to coincide with the resin pocket location. This allowed us to investigate the effect of different resin pockets on structural behaviour of the laminate.

The F.E. model simulating the 3-point bending experiment is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Finite element model for 3-point bending experiment

6 COMPARISON OF RESULTS

6.1 Resin pocket geometry

Figure 5 shows the predicted resin pocket geometry for both the square and curved inclusions in silicone and epoxy material. The F.E. predictions are overlaid on top of the microscopic cross-sections. As the magnifications of the used microscope are calibrated, the dimensional accuracy of the F.E. prediction can be compared to the experimental results.

Figure 5: Resin pocket prediction (black lines) overlaid on top of microscopic cross-sections

The results from Figure 5 clearly show the good correspondence between the experimental results and the F.E. predictions. The resin pocket dimensions and geometry are well predicted for both interrogator geometries and materials. The buckling of the underlying layers in the square inclusion samples is captured, although F.E. predictions indicate that all layers would buckle together, while experimental results show that the buckling is gradual from no buckling at the bottom ply to full buckling at the layer underneath the inclusion. This is an artefact of the modelling approach selected in this work, and cannot be overcome within the simulation. However, as this will over-emphasize the influence of the resin pocket, it will lead to safe designs.

6.2 Three point bending experiments

The cured samples are exposed to a three-point bending experiment as shown in Figure 6. The outer supports have a span of 270mm, and the support have a diameter of 16mm. The experimental samples have a layer of white paint applied to the front surface in order to make cracks and damage better visible. All tests are recorded using a video-camera synchronized to the data-logging of the tensile machine, in order to relate events in the force-displacement curve to visual events. All tests were performed on an INSTRON 5800R tensile load-frame with a 10kN load cell. Tests were performed up to failure of the specimen or maximum displacement of the test rig (67mm) at a speed of 6mm/min.

Figure 6: Three point bending set-up

In order to account for friction at the rollers, virgin samples of the material were tested and the force-displacement curve was recorded. These results were then used to tune the friction coefficient in F.E. simulations until good correspondence was achieved for the virgin material. This friction value was then used subsequently in all bending simulations of the samples with inclusions.

Figure 7 shows the comparison in force-displacement curves for a silicone inclusion between finite element simulations and experimental results.

Figure 7: Force-displacement curves for a silicone inclusion (black: experimental, red: finite element)

The results shown in Figure 7 illustrate the good correlation between experimental curves and finite element predictions, especially when taking into account that only elastic properties of the material were taken into account (as no failure data was available within the framework of this research). The results indicate that for both geometries, the specimen can withstand higher forces when the inclusion is located at the tension side of the bending load. This is a result of debonding between the silicone inclusion and laminate when compressive loads are applied. In addition, it can be seen that the square inclusion fails at a displacement of approximately 40mm, while the curved inclusion could not be broken within the displacement available in the test set-up (67mm). This illustrates that the concept of ‘*optimal geometries*’ indeed exists, and the predicted optimal shape performs better than a straight-forward square inclusion.

Figure 8 shows the results in force-displacement curves for an epoxy inclusion.

Figure 8: Force-displacement curves for an epoxy inclusion (black: experimental, red: finite element)

Again, the correspondence between F.E. and experiment is very good. In contrast to the silicone inclusions, the difference between the inclusion being located at the tensile or compressive side of the bending load is much smaller in these samples. This is a consequence of the better bonding between the laminate and the epoxy inclusion. Similar to the silicone samples, the square inclusions fail at 35mm, while the curved inclusion survives (in tension) the entire displacement range available. This emphasizes the better performance of the curved inclusion over a square inclusion.

Comparing silicone and epoxy inclusions, both materials have comparable force-displacement curves. As the epoxy inclusions perform better when located at the compression side of the specimen, these might be better suited for applications with fluctuating loads. It should be noted that these conclusions are from the composite point-of-view. In actual applications, additional considerations should be made regarding the stresses acting on the embedded electronics, in order to make sure that these can survive the applied loads.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a finite element approach was presented allowing the accurate finite element prediction of resin pocket geometries surrounding an embedded interrogator. A simple, straight-forward modelling approach was shown to achieve good results with microscopic images of experimental resin pockets. These predictions were used to simulate the loading response of a composite test coupon with embedded interrogator geometry under a three-point loading test. The resulting predicted force-displacement curves were compared to experimental results showing good correlation.

In addition, it was shown that the method was capable of accurately predicting the resin pockets and force-displacement curves for different inclusion geometries and materials. An optimal inclusion geometry – based on a minimization of resin pocket area – was proposed and shown to yield better performance in experimental bending tests compared to a standard square inclusion geometry. Using this technique, it becomes feasible to optimize the geometry of any inclusion in order to achieve the best performance under the desired loading conditions, and to determine the optimum material properties for the inclusion.

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